

SUPPLEMENTARY INFORMATION APPENDIX

A therapeutic small molecule enhances γ -oscillations and improves cognition/memory in Alzheimer's disease model mice

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Materials and Methods

Key resources table

REAGENT or RESOURCE	SOURCE	IDENTIFIER
Antibodies		
Anti-GABA(A)R alpha 1 subunit (guinea pig)	H. Mohler and J.-M. Fritschy, University of Zurich; Zurich; Switzerland	–
Anti-GABA(A)R alpha 1 subunit (extracellular) (guinea pig)	Alomone Labs Cat# AGP-083-GP	RRID:AB_2756618
Anti-GABA(A)R beta 2 subunit (rabbit)	PhosphoSolutions Cat# 862-GB2C	RRID:AB_2492109
Anti-GABA(A)R beta3 subunit (rabbit)	Millipore Cat# AB5563	RRID:AB_177525
Anti-GABA(A)R delta subunit (rabbit)	W. Sieghart, Center for Brain Research, Medical University of Vienna; Vienna; Austria. (Delta (17-60))	RRID:AB_2827804
Anti-Parvalbumin (rabbit)	K.G. Baimbridge, University of British Columbia; British Columbia; Canada (R301)	RRID:AB_2315236
Anti-Parvalbumin (mouse)	Millipore Cat# MAB1572	RRID:AB_2174013
Goat anti-Rabbit IgG (H+L) Highly Cross-Adsorbed Secondary Antibody, Alexa Fluor™ Plus 488	Thermo Fisher Scientific Cat# A32731	RRID:AB_2633280
Goat anti-Guinea Pig IgG (H+L) Highly Cross-Adsorbed Secondary Antibody, Alexa Fluor™ 488	Thermo Fisher Scientific Cat# A-11073	RRID:AB_2534117
Goat anti-Mouse IgG (H+L) Highly Cross-Adsorbed Secondary Antibody, Alexa Fluor™ 488	Thermo Fisher Scientific Cat# A-11029	RRID:AB_2534088

Goat anti-Guinea Pig IgG (H+L) Highly Cross-Adsorbed Secondary Antibody, Alexa Fluor™ 555	Thermo Fisher Scientific Cat# A-21435	RRID:AB_2535856
Goat anti-Rabbit IgG (H+L) Highly Cross-Adsorbed Secondary Antibody, Alexa Fluor™ Plus 555	Thermo Fisher Scientific Cat# A32732	RRID:AB_2633281
Biological samples		
Human liver microsomes	Thermo Fisher Scientific	HMMCPL
Blood plasma	Stemcell Technologies Inc	70039
Chemicals, peptides, and recombinant proteins		
NADPH	Millipore Sigma	10107824001
MgCl ₂	Millipore Sigma	M4880-100G
Acetonitrile	Thermo Fisher Scientific	A998-4
DMSO	Thermo Fisher Scientific	BP231-1
ProLong. Fluoromount G Mounting Medium	Thermo Fisher Scientific. Catalog number. P36934	RRID:SCR_015961
DDL-920	UCLA DDL	Ref XX
Critical commercial assays		
CHIRALPAK® CAN	Chiral Technologies	H15L-109
IAM.PC.DD	Regis Technologies	774011
Micro BCA™ Protein Assay Kit	Thermo Fisher Scientific	23235
Slide-A-Lyzer™ MINI Dialysis Devices	Thermo Fisher Scientific	PI88401
Deposited data		
β3 homopentameric GABA(A)R	RCSB Protein Data Bank (RCSB PDB)	4COF
β3δ heteropentameric GABA(A)R	RCSB Protein Data Bank (RCSB PDB)	7QND
Experimental models:Mus musculus		
C57BL/6J	Jackson Laboratory	RRID:IMSR_JAX:000664
Gabrd ^{-/-} mice on a C57BL/6J background	Jackson Laboratory	RRID:IMSR_JAX:003725
Pvalb-IRES-Cre mice	Jackson Laboratory	RRID:IMSR_JAX:0017320
B6.Cg-Gt(ROSA)26Sortm14(CAG-tdTomato)Hze/J	Jackson Laboratory	RRID:IMSR_JAX:0007914
ApoE4-TR:5xFAD mice	Greg Cole (UCLA)	
Software and algorithms		

ANY-maze software	Stoelting Co	RRID:SCR_014289
Cresset software	Flare v7.2	
Optibrium software	StarDrop 7.5	
Igor Pro 6.32, 7, 8, 9	Wavemetrics	RRID:SCR_000325
iSpy video motion analysis software	https://www.ispyconnect.com/	
ZEN Digital Imaging for Light Microscopy	Carl Zeiss light microscopy imaging systems	RRID:SCR_013672

Resource availability

Lead contact

Further information and requests for resources and reagents should be directed to and will be fulfilled by the lead contact, Istvan Mody (mody@ucla.edu).

Materials availability

All new material and mouse models generated from this study will be available upon request. Some may require MTAs.

Data and code availability

- Data and custom Igor procedures used for analysis will be uploaded to the Dryad data sharing website.
- Any additional information required to reanalyze the data reported in this work paper is available from the lead contact upon request.

Method details

Tissue collection for light microscopy

For immunohistochemistry studies, adult mice were deeply anesthetized with Fatal-Plus (90 mg/kg, i.p.) and perfused transcardially with 4% paraformaldehyde in 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 7.3). Brains were removed and postfixed for 1 h in the same fixative. Following cryoprotection, forebrain regions containing the hippocampus were frozen and sectioned coronally or sagittally at 30 μ m with a cryostat. Free-floating sections were stored in cryoprotectant for subsequent immunohistochemical studies.

Immunohistochemistry for light microscopy

Tissue processing and immunohistochemistry were performed with previously published methods (1). For double immunofluorescence labeling, free-floating sections (30 μ m) were incubated for 72 h at room temperature in the following combinations of primary antisera: 1) rabbit anti-parvalbumin (1:5,000; KG Baimbridge, R301) and either guinea pig anti- α 1 subunit (1:30,000; J-M Fritschy) or guinea pig anti- α 1 subunit (1:2,000; Alomone, AGA-001-GP); 2) rabbit anti- δ

subunit (1:3,000; W. Sieghart) and either mouse anti-parvalbumin (1:2,000; Millipore, MAB1572) or guinea pig anti- α 1 subunit (J-M Fritschy, as above); 3) guinea pig anti- α 1 subunit (Alomone, as above) and either rabbit anti- β 2 subunit (1:100; PhosphoSolutions, 862-GB2C) or anti- β 3 subunit (1:250; Millipore, AB5563). After thorough rinsing, sections were incubated with a combination of fluorescence-labeled secondary antisera (1:500), either 1) goat anti-rabbit IgG conjugated to Alexa Fluor Plus 488 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, A32731) and goat anti-guinea pig IgG conjugated to Alexa Fluor 555 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, A21435); or 2) goat anti-rabbit IgG conjugated to Alexa Fluor Plus 555 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, A32732) and either goat anti-guinea pig IgG conjugated to Alexa Fluor 488 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, A11073) or goat anti-mouse IgG conjugated to Alexa Fluor 488 (Thermo Fisher Scientific, A11029). Sections were incubated in secondary antisera for 4 h at room temperature, mounted on slides and cover slipped with anti-fade medium ProLong Diamond (Thermo Fisher Scientific).

Fluorescence-labeled sections were scanned with an LSM 880 confocal microscope (Carl Zeiss), and Z-stack images (0.2 or 1.0 μ m optical thickness) were acquired (excitation spectra 488 and 555nm) with 20x and 63x objectives. For double-labeled sections, optical slices were scanned separately for each label, alternating between the two channels in each section through the Z-stack. Confocal images were analyzed with Zen 2 software (Carl Zeiss).

Electrodes used for in vivo recordings

Electrodes (Plastics One) were stainless-steel, with polyimide electrode insulation, ending in a socket that fitted into the custom-made recording system. Electrode lengths (measured from bottom of socket contact to tip of wire) were 5 mm (for the two unilaterally implanted electrodes) and 25 mm for the ground/reference electrode. Electrode diameters were 125 μ m bare and 150 μ m insulated. The two unilaterally implanted electrodes were custom made as follows: a socket (gold-plated stainless steel Amphenol contact, O.D: 1.07 mm, I.D: 0.686 mm and length: 7.87 mm) was attached to a flexible 10 mm long PFA Teflon insulated wire. The free tip of this wire was soldered to another 3 mm long Amphenol socket attached to the 5 mm electrode. The openings of the sockets were trimmed to 1 mm length, cleaned from debris, smoothed on the edges and tightened. The three electrodes were assembled into one unit by connecting their sockets with J-B Weld™ two-part epoxy. The space between the sockets corresponded to the distance between the three Amphenol pins soldered to the recording preamplifier.

Stereotaxic surgeries

The two recording electrodes were implanted bilaterally in the ventral hippocampal CA1 region at -3.3 AP, 3.5 ML, 3 DV (AP, anterior-posterior; ML, medial-lateral; DV, dorsal-ventral) according to established coordinates (2) and from the ALLEN Mouse Brain Atlas, Version 2 (2011), Allen Institute for Brain Science. These coordinates consistently positioned the electrodes in the pyramidal cell layer or slightly above it, as judged by the depth profile of the relationship between θ -phase and γ -oscillations (3) in the shape of the recorded SPW-R complexes (4,5). The reference/ground electrode was implanted over the cerebellum. The skull and the lower part of the electrode unit system was then covered with Ortho-Jet™ acrylic resin. During the surgery, lidocaine (2 μ l from 2% solution) was injected subcutaneously on the neck and the nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drug Rimadyl (Carprofen) (0.1 mg/kg) was administered intraperitoneally for pain management (Rimadyl was additionally administered for two consecutive days). In addition, 50 μ l sterile saline was administered subcutaneously for hydration during surgery. During recovery after

surgery (one week) mice were single housed in plastic disposable cages with a plastic lid that did not interfere with the head implants.

In vivo recordings and data acquisition

The electrical signals from the mouse brain were relayed through a custom-made recording system to a computer, located outside the recording room. Briefly 1-1.5 m long cable was constructed using 8 intertwined bare copper wires (single 8058-Magnet Wire) and placed inside a PVC tubing. The cable was soldered accordingly to a LT1112S8#PBF General Purpose Amplifier 2 Circuit 8-SO (Digi-Key) on one end and to a MMA25-011 connector plug with male pins (Digi-Key) to the other end. The connector plug end of the cable was attached to a 10-channel slip ring commutator (Campden Instruments). Both ends of the cable were covered with J-B Weld™ two-part epoxy. The commutator was joined to a custom-made connector box that also contained two 9 V batteries providing the power supply to the preamplifier. The signal was then transmitted to Model 3600 16 channel amplifier (A-M Systems) (LP: 300 Hz, HP: 0.3 Hz Gain:1K). The output signal was led to an USB 6009 14 bit A/D converter (National Instruments) connected to a laptop computer. Igor 8.0 (Wavemetrics) NIDAQ tools system was used to record the two channels in each mouse at a sampling rate of 2048 s⁻¹. During the continuous recording sessions, the mice were housed in clear polycarbonate containers (32 cm diameter and 38 cm high, Cambro) with the floor covered by bedding. Food, water, and nest material were also added. The video rate captured by an infrared-sensitive USB camera was 11-13 frames/s providing a movement resolution of ~76-90 ms. The iSpy software was used to determine the motion of the animals through a frame-by-frame subtraction of successive video images. The threshold for movement detection of the software was set to 80 pixels.

Analysis of in vivo LFP recordings

All data analyses were carried out using custom written procedures in IgorPro 8.0 and 9.0 (Wavemetrics) using its built-in functions for RMS measurement, FIR filtering, FFT, Hilbert amplitude, etc. The rest of the analyses such as Morlet wavelet transform, spectral peak detection, PAC, and FAC were done using procedures written in Igor 8.0 based on published methods. First, using a FIR filter (using at least 401 coefficients or with the number of coefficients determined as = $\text{int}(50/(22*(\text{HF}-\text{LF})/\text{SR}))$, where int is the integer part, 50 is the cutoff of the filter in dB, HF and LF are the high and low frequencies, respectively of the bandpass, and SR is the sampling rate (2048 s⁻¹). We bandpass filtered the raw recordings, at 0.5-4 Hz for δ , 5-12 Hz for θ and 30-120 Hz for γ oscillations. This digital FIR filtering did not change the phase of the oscillations (5). The band-pass filtered traces were then used for calculating the RMS values for the analyses.

Several recording segments of 120 s duration were selected during intervals of 1-3 hrs before and within 2-3 hrs after the administration of drug or vehicle. The criterion for selection was based on the RMS of θ -oscillations that had to be larger during the entire duration of the 120 s epoch, than the mean + 3xSD of the average RMS of the θ -band-filtered recording for the entire 12 hr period. The choice of the θ -oscillations for the selection was to avoid bias by selecting segments based on the power of γ -oscillations. One segment pre- and one after the drug or vehicle administration was each selected randomly from those that satisfied the selection criterion. We used published methods (6-9) to calculate the modulation indices of γ oscillations by θ oscillation frequency or phase. We used two methods to determine the coupling of θ oscillation phase to γ oscillation amplitude. In the first method we started by isolating the individual θ cycles from the θ -filtered traces during the 8 s epochs yielding about 50-70 cycles in total. Then, each θ cycle was divided

into equal time segments each corresponding to $\pi/10$ radians of the given θ cycle. The γ bandwidth filtered traces were then aligned with these time segments and their peak-to-peak amplitudes and frequencies were measured. The median values of these amplitudes were entered into a matrix in the corresponding γ -frequency row binned by 10 Hz from 30-120 Hz. The matrix was complete when all the θ cycles during the 8 s epoch were analyzed. The second method used the Hilbert transform of the θ bandwidth filtered signal over the 8 s epoch to calculate the continuous phase of the θ oscillations. Over each phase of the θ cycle thus obtained, the raw signals were filtered in 10 Hz bins between 30-120 Hz (9 bins in total) and the amplitude histograms of these band-filtered signals were plotted over each θ phase. The two methods yielded nearly identical PAC results, but we decided to show the graphs obtained by the first method. Once the various modulation matrices were obtained for at least 10 different 8 s periods during the same chosen 120 s epoch, we averaged the matrices. The resulting averages were converted to a Z-scale (Fig. 3D) for every 10 Hz of the γ -frequency band and were smoothed by a 2D spline algorithm (ImageInterpolate function of Igor 8.0). The spectrograms of the long-duration recordings were obtained by using the Short-Time Fourier Transform (STFT) function of Igor Pro 8.0 or 9.0 with using a Hanning window with a segments size of 60 s (122,880 points) and a 30 s overlap.

Slice preparation

Mice were at least 3-months-old when the ex vivo experiments were undertaken. They were anesthetized with isoflurane and decapitated following UCLA Chancellor's Animal Research Committee protocol. Horizontal 350 μm thick slices were cut on a Leica VT1200S vibratome in ice-cold N-Methyl-D-Glutamine (NMDG)-based HEPES-buffered solution, containing (in mM): 135 NMDG, 10 D-glucose, 4 MgCl_2 , 0.5 CaCl_2 , 1 KCl, 1.2 KH_2PO_4 , 20 HEPES, 27 sucrose (bubbled with 100% O_2 , pH 7.4, 290-300 mOsm/L). Then, slices were incubated at 32°C in a reduced sodium artificial CSF (ACSF), containing (in mM): NaCl 85, D-glucose 25, sucrose 55, KCl 2.5, NaH_2PO_4 1.25, CaCl_2 0.5, MgCl_2 4, NaHCO_3 26, pH 7.3-7.4 when bubbled with 95% O_2 , 5% CO_2 . After 30 min low sodium ACSF was substituted for normal ACSF at room temperature, containing (in mM): NaCl 126, D-glucose 10, MgCl_2 2, CaCl_2 2, KCl 2.5, NaH_2PO_4 1.25, Na Pyruvate 1.5, L-Glutamine 1, NaHCO_3 26, pH 7.3-7.4 when bubbled with 95% O_2 , 5% CO_2 . All salts were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich.

In vitro gamma oscillations

Kainic acid (KA, Tocris) was used to generate gamma γ -oscillations in slices. To get a stable level of γ -oscillations after the slice cutting and recovery incubation period, the slices were incubated for at least 30 min in ACSF containing 50 nM KA before transferring them to the recording chamber (10,11). Recordings were done in an interface chamber at 34°C perfused with normal ACSF also containing 50 nM KA at a speed of 5 ml/min. Oscillatory network activity was recorded in CA3 stratum pyramidale with the use of a patch pipette (3-5 $\text{M}\Omega$ resistance) filled with KA-containing ACSF connected to the headstage of an amplifier (A-M Systems Inc., model 3000). The signal was band-pass filtered between 0.1 and 1000 Hz and then was fed through an instrumentation amplifier (Brownlee BP Precision, model 210A) and sampled at 4096 s^{-1} with a National Instruments A/D board. Field potentials were recorded using a custom LabView software (EVAN) and analyzed with a custom written procedure (Wavemetrics, IGOR Pro 8). Peak frequencies, power at peak frequency and total power were obtained from the corresponding RMS, averaged from 60 s recording periods.

Patch clamp recordings and analyses

For recording, brain slices were transferred to a submerged recording chamber at 34°C and perfused at 5 ml/min with ACSF. Slices were visualized under IR-DIC upright microscope (Olympus BX-51WI, 20x XLUMPlan FL N objective) and whole-cell recordings were obtained from either dentate gyrus granule cells, somatosensory pyramidal cells, or PV+INs labeled with tdTomato with borosilicate patch pipettes (4-6 M Ω , King Precision Glass) containing of internal solutions (ICS) (in mM): 140 Cs-met, 2 MgCl₂ 10 HEPES, 0.2 EGTA, 2 Na₂-ATP, 0.2 Na₂-GTP. The pH of the ICS was adjusted to 7.2 with CsOH and its osmolarity was 285-290 mOsm. ICS were stored at -80°C in 1 ml aliquots. Before each experiment, ICS aliquots were thawed to room temperature and kept on ice during recording. Recordings were obtained using an Axon-patch 200B amplifier (Molecular Devices, San Jose, CA, USA), low-pass filtered at 5 kHz (Bessel, 8-pole) and digitized at 10 kHz with a National Instruments data acquisition board (BNC 2110, National Instruments, Austin, TX, USA). All data were acquired with EVAN (custom-designed LabView-based software). Spontaneous inhibitory post synaptic currents (sIPSCs) were recorded at a holding potential (V_h) of 0 mV. Whole-cell capacitance were estimated from fast transients evoked by a 5 mV voltage command step using lag values of 7 μ s and then compensated to 70-80%. The series resistance was monitored before and after the recording, recordings with series resistances >20 M Ω or a change >20% during the recording were excluded.

A custom written procedure in IGOR Pro 8.0 (Wavemetrics) was used to perform the analysis of tonic and phasic currents (12). An all-points histogram of a randomly selected recording segment of 30 s during the period of interest was plotted. A Gaussian was fitted to the part of the distribution from the minimum value at the left to the rightmost (largest) value of the histogram distribution. The mean value of the fitted Gaussian was taken as the tonic current (I_{tonic}) after subtracting the mean value of a Gaussian fitted to the residual current recorded in the presence of saturating concentration (40 μ M) of the GABA_AR antagonist gabazine (12). The skewed distribution toward synaptic events (I_{phasic}). This process was repeated for all segments of interest.

In Silico Screening

There is no crystal or cryo-EM structural study of the $\alpha 1\beta 2\delta$ GABA_AR complex. This is available for the $\beta 3$ homopentameric and the $\beta 3\delta$ heteropentameric GABA_AR, the $\beta 2$ and $\beta 3$ receptors have a sequence similarity of >95% in their ligand binding and membrane spanning domains (13). Therefore, we used it in our in silico screening. Small molecules of various structural classes were docked into the model prepared from the known crystal structure of the $\beta 3$ homopentameric GABA_AR (pdb:4COF) (13). Docking of the structures was performed using Flare v7.2 (Cresset software) and the binding score of the docked structure in the model was determined. This analysis led to the identification of DDL-920 that showed good binding with a Lead Finder (LF) rank score of -10.35 in the docking simulation (*SI Appendix*, Fig. 4A). To determine if DDL-920 would bind and interact with a GABA_AR containing the δ -subunit we used the published $\beta 3\delta$ heteropentameric GABA_AR structure (pdb:7QND)¹⁴. The docking simulation with DDL-920 and structure pdb:7QND reveals that in the presence of the δ -subunit it reaches a better LF rank score of -11.21 compared to docking to pdb:4COF. The model also reveals that DDL-920 makes key interactions with both the $\beta 3$ and δ subunits of pdb:7QND (*SI Appendix*, Fig. 4B). Additionally, predictive analysis for brain permeability and other drug-like properties was done *in silico* using StarDrop (Optibrium software) analysis platform. The analysis showed that DDL-920 would be brain permeable and with good drug-like properties. Hence it was selected for synthesis and testing in our *in vitro* assays and *in vivo* model.

Pharmacokinetics (PK) in mice

All *in vivo* experiments described were carried out in strict accordance with good animal practice according to NIH recommendations. All procedures for animal use were approved by the Animal Research Committee (ARC) at UCLA and under an approved ARC protocol.

Wildtype (WT) C57Bl6 mice were dosed by oral (gavage or pipette) or subcutaneous (SC) injection at 3 doses (1, 5, 10 mg/kg), and animals were euthanized 1, 3 and 6 hours after administration by ketamine/xylazine over-anesthesia following by transcardial collection of blood for isolation of plasma and saline perfusion. Brain tissue was collected *post-mortem* for assessment of compound levels.

Analysis of brain concentrations was done at the UCLA Pasarow Mass Spectrometry Lab (PMSL; Kym Faull, Ph.D., Director). A targeted liquid chromatography-tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) assay was developed for DDL-920 using the multiple reaction monitoring (MRM) acquisition method on a 6460 triple quadrupole mass spectrometer (Agilent Technologies) coupled to a 1290 Infinity HPLC system (Agilent Technologies) with a Phenomenex analytical column (Gemini-NX 3 μ m C18 110 Å 100 x 2.0 mm). The HPLC method utilized a mixture of solvent A (99.9/1 Water/Formic Acid) and solvent B (99.9/1 Acetonitrile/Formic Acid) and a gradient was used for the elution of the compounds (min/%B: 0/0, 5/0, 20/99, 22/99, 25/0, 35/0).

In this assay, detection of a fragment ions originating from DDL-920 (m/z : 308.1 \rightarrow 141, 235) as well as LC retention time (RT= 11 min) were utilized to ensure compound specificity and accurate quantification in the biological samples. An internal standard (IS) that closely resembled DDL-920 (m/z : 361; 100 pmol; RT = 14.9) was added to every sample to account for compound loss during sample processing. Standards were made in drug naïve plasma and brain lysates with increasing amounts of cambinol (S1, S2: 0 pmol/ S3,S4: 1 pmol/ S5,S6: 10 pmol/ S7,S8: 100 pmol, S9,S10: 1000 pmol). The standard curve was made by plotting the amount of DDL-920 per standard vs. the ratio of measured chromatographic peak areas for each compound (DDL-920/IS). The trendline equation was then used to calculate the absolute concentrations of DDL-920 in the brain tissue.

Efficacy testing in E4FAD mice

Male and female 3-month-old mice were administered DDL-920 via pipette feeding by the method of Atcha et al¹⁵ at a dose of 10 mg/kg BID (20 mg/kg/day). Mice were weighed before the first dose for the calculation of volume to be administered. The formulation used comprised DDL-920 as a 10 mg/mL solution dissolve first in water and then in strawberry syrup (50 V/V final water concentration). Mice were dosed for 2 weeks BID (*SI Appendix*, Fig. S9) before entering Barnes Maze testing as described by Attar et al. (14). Briefly, in a room with visual cues on the walls, mice are introduced in a circular maze containing 20 holes where 19 holes are closed during training and all 20 holes are closed during the probe trials. On day 1 of the habituation stage, mice are placed at the center of the maze inside the start chamber. After 10 s the start chamber is removed, and mice are allowed to explore the maze for 3 min. After 3 min of exploration, the mice are guided to the target (escape) hole and allowed to stay there for 2 min. After habituation, mice undergo 3 consecutive training days, and each training day is comprised of 3 trials. Each trial starts with the mice being placed at the center of the maze inside the start chamber for 10 s. After this the start chamber is removed and mice are allowed to explore the maze for 3 min. If during this time they do not find the target hole, they are guided to it and allowed to remain inside for 1 min. At the end of each training day mice were dosed at 10 mg/kg. Next are the 24- and 48-hours probe days. During the probe days, the target hole is closed, and spatial memory of the mouse is determined during a

90 s probe trial. Mice are placed at the center of the maze inside the start chamber, after 10 s the start chamber is removed, and mice are allowed to explore the maze for 90 s. At the end of the trial, the mice are returned to the home cage and dose at 10 mg/kg. The ANY-maze software (Stoelting) was used to analyze the behavior of the mice in the Barnes Maze. Over the course of the training and probe trials, the software-calculated parameters included, but were not limited to, total distance traveled, speed, number of holes visited, latency to visiting the target/escape hole, percent time spent in the four quadrants of the maze.

Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism. Excretion (ADME)

Methods for determination of kinetic solubility, plasma stability, liver microsome stability, parallel artificial membrane permeability assay (PAMPA), plasma protein (human serum albumin, HSA) binding, and brain tissue binding are described next.

Kinetic solubility assay

DDL-920 (10 mM, 100% DMSO) was diluted separately into aqueous buffer (100 μ M; PBS pH 7.4) and DMSO at various concentrations (1000, 100, 10, 1, 0.1 μ M). The solutions were incubated at 37°C for 90 min and centrifuged at 16K x g for 5 min. An aliquot of each supernatant was analyzed by LC-MS/MS. A standard curve was generated by plotting the known amount of analyte per standard in DMSO vs. chromatographic peak area. Kinetic solubility (mM) was calculated using the trendline equation with maximum chromatographic peak area observed in the aqueous DDL-920 sample (15).

Liver microsome stability assay

A 1 μ L sample of 1 mM DDL-920 in 100% DMSO was added to 1 mL of 0.5 mg/mL human liver microsomes (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Cat# HMMCPL) in PBS pH 7.4, 2 mM NADPH, and 2 mM $MgCl_2$; and incubated at 37 °C for 120 min. Aliquots (50 μ L) of the microsome solution were taken at timepoints of 0, 5, 10, 15, 30, 60, 90, and 120 min, and added to a 200 μ L 100% acetonitrile reaction quenching solution containing an internal standard. Solutions were clarified by centrifugation (16K x g, 5 min) and supernatants transferred to new tubes and lyophilized. Samples were reconstituted in 100 μ L of 50/50/0.1 water/acetonitrile/formic acid prior to analysis via LC-MS/MS¹⁸. Normalized chromatographic peak areas were plotted at each time point and the half-life ($T_{1/2}$) of compound in liver microsomes was determined by using the trendline equation to calculate the time at which compound abundance was 50% of that at timepoint 0 (T_0).

Plasma stability assay

A 1 μ L DDL-920 (1 mM in 100% DMSO) was added to human peripheral blood plasma (Cat#70039, Stemcell Technologies Inc) diluted 2-fold in PBS (1000 μ L, pH 7.4) and incubated at 37°C for 180 min. Aliquots (50 μ L) of the plasma solution were taken at 0, 15, 30, 60, 90, 120, 150, and 180 min, and added to a 200 μ L 100% acetonitrile reaction quenching solution containing an internal standard. Solutions were clarified by centrifugation (16K x g, 5 min) and supernatants were transferred to new tubes and lyophilized. Samples were reconstituted in 100 μ L of 50/50/0.1 water/acetonitrile/formic acid prior to analysis via LC-MS/MS).

Normalized chromatographic peak areas were plotted at each time point and the $T_{1/2}$ in plasma was determined by using the trendline equation to calculate the time at which compound abundance was 50% of that at timepoint 0 (T_0).

Human serum albumin (HSA) binding assay

The liquid chromatography-ultraviolet/visible spectroscopy (LC-UV/Vis) assay was performed on a 1290 Infinity HPLC system (Agilent Technologies) with an HPLC column containing immobilized HSA (CHIRALPAK® CAN, Chiral Technologies, Cat#H15L-109, 5 µm 50 x 4 mm). The HPLC method utilized an isocratic gradient containing 100% 6.7 mM phosphate buffer saline (pH 7.4). The retention time of the compound (t_r) and injection peak were recorded.

The percent protein binding (P) was calculated using the following equations:

$$K' = (t_r - t_m) / t_m; P = 100 \times [K' / (K' + 1)]$$

Parallel artificial membrane permeability assay (PAMPA)

A liquid chromatography-ultraviolet/visible spectroscopy (LC-UV/Vis) assay was performed on a 1290 Infinity HPLC system (Agilent Technologies) with an HPLC column containing immobilized phosphatidylcholine (IAM.PC.DD, Regis Technologies, Cat#774011, 5 µm 300 Å 100 x 4.6 mm). The HPLC buffer comprised 6.7 mM PBS (pH 7.4; solvent A) and acetonitrile (solvent B): a gradient was used for the elution of the compounds (min/%B: 0/20, 20/60, 21/20, 30/20). The retention time of the compound (t_r) and void volume time of the column (t_0) were recorded.

Membrane permeability (P_m) was calculated using the following equations as described (16).

$$\text{KIAM} = (t_r - t_0) / t_0; P_m = (\text{KIAM} / \text{MW}_4) \times 10^{10}$$

Compounds with a P_m >0.85 are predicted to be blood-brain barrier (BBB) permeable (CNS+) at pH 7.4 (17).

Brain Tissue Binding Assay

Brain tissue was homogenized in PBS (pH 7.4) (1: 3 weight(mg)/volume(µL)) and the protein concentration determined using the Micro BCA™ Protein Assay Kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Cat#23235). Brain homogenate was diluted to 20 mg/mL in PBS (pH 7.4) and added to Slide-A-Lyzer™ MINI Dialysis Devices, 10K MWCO dialysis cups (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Cat#PI88401) in a 48-well plate containing PBS (500 µL; pH 7.4). 1 µL of 1 mM compound was added to the brain homogenate (final concentration: 2 µM compound, 0.5% DMSO) and incubated on a rocker for 4.5 hours at 37°C. 50 µL of brain homogenate (within the dialysis cup) and PBS (within the 48-well plate) were transferred to new microcentrifuge tubes containing 200 µL of quenching reagent (100% acetonitrile) containing internal standard. Solutions were clarified by centrifugation (16,000 x g, 5 min) and the supernatants were transferred to new tubes and lyophilized. Samples were reconstituted in 100 µL of 50/50/0.1 (Water/Acetonitrile/Formic Acid) prior to analysis via LC-MS/MS. The % of the unbound drug was calculated using the following equation: $f_{\text{unbound}} = [\text{normalized peak area in buffer side} / \text{normalized peak area in brain side}] \times 100$.

Quantification and statistical analysis

All statistical analyses are clearly indicated in the text or figure legends. We used the various built-in statistical functions of Igor Pro 8.0 or 9.0 for the statistical comparisons. The measure of dispersion was the SEM, unless otherwise noted. Mean values, and occasionally median values are given. The p-values for the various statistical comparisons are clearly indicated in the main text, figure legends, or in the figures themselves. The numbers of replicates are always given, and it is clearly specified what these numbers refer to.

Supplementary Figures, Table, and Legends

Figure S1 | PV+ interneurons along the base of the granule cell layer express both the δ and $\alpha 1$ subunits. (A-C) The majority of PV+ interneurons along the inner border of the granule cell layer express the δ subunit (examples at arrows). (D-F) Virtually all PV+INs along the granule cell border also express the $\alpha 1$ subunit (examples at arrows). Such labeling supports the localization of δ and $\alpha 1$ subunits in these PV+ interneurons and their possible subunit partnership. Scale bars: A-F = 50 μm .

Figure S2 | $\alpha 1$ subunit-labeled interneurons at the base of the granule cell layer express δ and $\beta 2$ subunits. (A) δ subunit labeling (arrows) is evident in the cell bodies of $\alpha 1$ -labeled interneurons. (B) $\beta 2$ subunit labeling (arrows) is extensively co-localized on the surface of $\alpha 1$ -labeled cell bodies and dendritic processes. (C) $\beta 3$ subunit shows little localization on the $\alpha 1$ -labeled interneurons and is concentrated in small punctate structures in the dentate molecular layer (*). These localization patterns support a receptor subunit partnership of δ , $\alpha 1$ and $\beta 2$ in these interneurons. Scale bars: A,B,C = 20 μm .

Figure S3 | DDL-920 PK studies by subcutaneous, oral gavage, or oral pipette administration. (A) Brain concentrations and levels of DDL-920 after subcutaneous administration at 1, 5 and 10 mg/kg; (B) Brain concentrations and levels of DDL-920 after oral gavage at 5 and 10 mg/kg, or by pipette administration at 10 mg/kg.

Figure S4 | DDL-920 docking to GABA_ARs. (A) Docking of DDL-920 to the $\beta 3$ homopentameric GABA_AR (pdb: 4COF) gave a good lead finder (LF) rank score (-10.34) and shows key interactions with Phe200 and Tyr62 of the β subunit; (B) Docking to the $\beta 3\delta$ heteropentameric GABA_AR structure (pdb: 7QND) gave a better LF rank score (-11.21) and shows how DDL-920 interacts with both the δ subunit (δ -E) and with the β subunit ($\beta 3$ -D). The key interactions of DDL-920 for $\beta 3$ -subunit was include Tyr62 and Asp43, while the key interaction for the δ -subunit was with Lys229 and Glu183.

Figure S5 | Related to Fig. 3 | Spectrograms of 4 hr recording periods of γ -oscillations. *Top:* Spectrogram of the hippocampal γ -oscillations 4 hrs before a 10 mg/kg DDL-920 SQ injection on Day 0 (Fig. 3) of a WT mouse. *Bottom:* Spectrogram of the hippocampal γ -oscillations for a duration 4 hrs commencing about 20 min after a 10 mg/kg DDL-920 SQ injection on Day 0 (Fig. 3) of a WT mouse. Calibration bar is 30 min, and refers to both panels. For color scale values, please see *S/Appendix*, Fig. 7.

Figure S6 | Related to Fig. 3 | Spectrograms of 4 hr recording periods of γ -oscillations. *Top:* Spectrogram of the hippocampal γ -oscillations 4 hrs before a SQ saline injection on Day 3 (Fig. 3) of a WT mouse. White bars indicate periods where the spectrograms were biased by excessive electrical/mechanical noise in the recording apparatus. *Bottom:* Spectrogram of the hippocampal γ -oscillations for a duration of 4 hrs commencing about 30 min after SQ saline injection on Day 3 (Fig. 3) of a WT mouse. Calibration bar is 30 min, and refers to both panels. For color scale values, please see *SI Appendix*, Fig. 7.

Figure S7 | Related to Fig. 3 | Spectrograms of 4 hr recording periods of γ -oscillations. *Top:* Spectrogram of the hippocampal γ -oscillations for 4 hrs before a 10 mg/kg DDL-920 SQ injection on Day 24 (Fig. 3) of a WT mouse. *Bottom:* Spectrogram of the hippocampal γ -oscillations for a duration of 4 hrs commencing about 15 min after a 10 mg/kg DDL-920 SQ injection on Day 24 (Fig. 3) of a WT mouse. Calibration bar is 30 min, and refers to both panels. Color scale values are in μV^2 .

Figure S8 | Related to Fig. 4A-C. The power (RMS) of γ -oscillations in an AD mouse following oral pipette administration of DDL-920 (10 mg/kg). (A) *Top panel:* The average RMS of the γ -oscillations was calculated every 5 min for a period of 12 hrs (from 6:00 to 18:00 hrs). The drug administration was done at the time indicated by a black vertical bar. The dashed line before the DDL-920 administration is the linear fit to the \sim 4 hrs of recordings (*gray box*) except for the first 45 min of the recording when the animals are usually winding down from the time spent in the dark. The same fitted line was extended to the post drug administration period, allowing for 1 hr of recovery after the animal has been handled during the drug administration. It appears that the effect of DDL-920 on γ -oscillation power lasts more than 4.5 hrs, which constitutes a good estimate of its pharmacodynamics. *Bottom panel:* The corresponding motor activity of the mouse, also averaged every 5 min, as derived from the video recordings, is plotted on the same x-axis to illustrate no change in behavior. (B) Histogram of the points during the shaded periods of A. The RMS means (\pm SD) were $26.1 \pm 4.1 \mu V^2$ prior to DDL-920 administration, and $30.1 \pm 3.5 \mu V^2$ after the drug administration ($p = 1.13e-6$, t-test).

Figure S9 | Efficacy testing for DDL-920 on memory in the AD mouse model. DDL-920 testing in the ApoE4-TR:5xFAD mice was done by oral pipette administration at 10 mg/kg twice daily (BID) for 2-weeks followed by Barnes Maze memory testing during the third week. The mouse, pipettor, vial, and Barnes Maze in the figure have been adapted from www.biorender.com.

Figure S10 | Mouse motility in the Barnes maze during the training period and the probe trials. The total distance run by the three groups of mice in the Barnes maze did not differ significantly between the groups, neither during the training trial periods, nor during the 24 hr or 48 hr probe trials. Points represent means, error bars are SEM.

Property or ADME Parameter	Measured	Desired
Molecular weight [g/mol]	342.86	>160 & <480
Ratio of sp ³ hybridized C : total C count (Fraction Csp ³)	0.32	>0.25
Number of rotatable bonds	3	<8
Number of H-bond acceptors	3	<7
Number of H-bond donors	2	<3
Kinetic solubility [μ M]	>100	> 5
Microsomal stability [$t_{1/2}$ (min)]	>120	>60
Plasma stability [$t_{1/2}$ (min)]	>150	>180
Plasma binding [F_{unbound} (%)]	14.6	>10
BBB permeability PAMPA [P_m]	6.0	>0.85
Brain: Plasma ratio	0.714	>0.5
Brain tissue binding [F_{unbound} (%)]	34	>10
Oral (pipette) brain pharmacokinetics [C_{max} (nM)]	23	
Unbound brain concentration [C_{max} (nM)]	8	
In vitro efficacious dose [nM]	1	

SMILES structure: On1cc(c(n1)Cc1ccc2c(c1)ccc2)C1CCNCC1

Chemical structure:

Table S1 | Physico-chemical properties (18) and in vitro absorption, distribution, metabolism and excretion (ADME) data (15,17,19,20) and structure of DDL-920. The drug-like properties of DDL-920 have desirable properties for further drug development.

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